
Electron Identification with the Central Arm Spectrometers and Silicon Vertex Detector at PHENIX

Dillon Fitzgerald (1) and Roli Esha (2)

Physics Department, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, MI 48109 USA (1)

Physics Department, Stony Brook University, Stony Brook, NY 11795 USA (2)

Abstract

This document outlines the procedure for identifying electrons using the central arm spectrometers and silicon vertex detector within the PHENIX framework, as well as the procedure for creating an analysis module to process full datasets with the analysis taxi.

June 2021

Contents

1	Introduction	2
2	Electron identification	2
3	Building the analysis module	4
4	Committing the module	5
5	The Gatekeeper	6
5.1	cppcheck	6
5.2	Valgrind	7
5.3	Insure	8
6	Submitting to the Analysis Taxi	8
7	Characteristics plots	9
8	Additional Information	11

1 Introduction

The analysis modules within the PHENIX framework are submitted CVS and are run using the analysis taxi. In this document, detailed instructions for writing code to identify electrons, submitting the analysis module to CVS, and processing full datasets with your analysis module using the analysis taxi are provided.

It is not advisable to work in the home directory due to space restrictions. Hence, once your PHENIX account is set up, please request for space on the working group disk (e.g. Spin, PLHF, HHJ). This is where the taxi output is written.

2 Electron identification

Within the PHENIX detector setup, information from the Drift Chamber (DC), the Ring Imaging Cherenkov detector (RICH) Electromagnetic Calorimeter (EMCal) and Silicon Vertex detector (SVX) is used to identify electrons. The DC, RICH, and EMCal information is accessed through the PHCentralTrack node, while the SVX information is accessed through the SvxCentralTrackList node. Note that in order to analyze a PHCentralTrack that has a corresponding SvxCentralTrack, you will need to use the SvxCentralTrack->getDchIndex() function and provide this index to the PHCentralTracks node.

The most important criteria for electron identification are:

- The quality of the track which is given by the hit pattern in the DC.

$$\text{quality} = 63 \parallel 51 \parallel 31$$

- Minimum momentum for a reliable reconstruction of the track.

$$p_T > 0.15 \text{ GeV}$$

- The z extent of the DC.

$$|zed| < 75 \text{ cm}$$

- The number of photo-tubes fired in RICH.

$$n0 > 0$$

- The distance between the ring center and track projection in RICH.

$$disp < 5$$

- The ratio of energy (from EMCal) to momentum (from DC) of a given track ($E/p = ecore/p$). Sometimes, it is preferred to consider $(E/p - \mu)/\sigma$ to make it momentum independent and, hence, increase the purity (dep).

$$ecore/p > 0.5 \quad \text{or} \quad -2 < dep < 5$$

- Shower shape in the EMCal

$$\chi^2/npe0 < 10$$

- The probability of the shower in the associated subcluster being electromagnetic.

$$prob > 0.01$$

- Matching of the track between DC and EMCal. This cut can also be signalized to match within 5 sigma.

$$EMCdz < 20 \text{ cm}; EMCd\phi < 0.05 \quad \text{or} \quad |EMCsdz| < 5; |EMCsd\phi| < 5$$

- DC side = RICH side = PC1 side to avoid side crossing tracks.
 - Note: this is less important for p+p where there are lower track multiplicities, so it is not considered in the example code

Other cuts can be introduced depending on the analysis and the desired purity of the electron candidates. For example, information from the SVX can be used in addition to the central arm spectrometers to increase electron purity and mitigate conversion electrons.

- Quality of the fit of the SVXCentralTrack to hits in the SVX, this cut was chosen such that only reliably fitted tracks are analyzed.

$$\chi^2/ndf < 3$$

- Pattern of hits in the SVX, the cut is applied with a bitwise operator which requires at least one hit in each of the inner two layers of the VTX, removing background from photonic conversions.

$$(hitpattern\&3) == 3$$

- Number of hits in the SVX, this cut helps to ensure higher quality SVX tracks and remove background from photonic conversions.

$$nhit > 2$$

- Conversion veto cut using SVX information with varying scale factors for Δz $\Delta\phi$ window sizes (1x, 1.5x, 2x, 4x, 10x), the cut becoming more stringent with larger window size. The 2x window size was determined to yield the most optimal signal to background ratio in previous Run 15 p+p analyses. The conversion veto algorithm used in the example analysis module was developed within the VTX WG.

$$\text{ConversionVeto} = \text{True}$$

You may also be interested in saving the following variables for further analysis, which are relevant for c/b separation studies using the SVX.

- Distance of closest transverse approach to beam center.

$$DCA2D$$

- Distance of closest longitudinal approach to beam center.

$$DCAZ$$

The selection requirements can be tightened or loosened depending on the analysis in question in order to balance statistics and electron purity of the data sample. One recommendation is to use modest selection requirements at first (e.g. $n0 > 0$ only) and save the relevant variables into a tree or ntuple such that selection requirements can be applied and adjusted later as desired, as shown in the following analysis module.

3 Building the analysis module

The analysis module is a folder containing all the files used to run the code on taxi. The main ingredients are the following:

- `autogen.sh`
- `configure.ac`
- `Makefile.am`
- Analysis files in class structure (`*.C` and `*.h` and `*LinkDef.h`)

A ready-to-run explicit example can be found at

```
offline/AnalysisTrain/ExampleElectronSvxAnalysis
```

`ExampleElectronAnalysis` contains the following files:

- `autogen.sh`
- `configure.ac`
- `Makefile.am`
- `ExampleElectronSvxAnalysis.*`
 - This is a class to process events and to create and fill TTrees
- `ConversionVeto.*`
 - This is a class for using SVX information to veto conversion electrons
- `MyAnalysis.C`
 - This is an example macro to run on the produced TTrees from the `ExampleElectronSvxAnalysis` class and apply all electron identification cuts listed in this document. Note that this type of macro is NOT standard to include in your analysis module, which is typically reserved for processing DSTs rather than taxi output, but I include it here for completeness.

All analysis modules are available at

<https://phenix-intra.sdcc.bnl.gov/viewvc/viewvc.cgi/phenix/offline/AnalysisTrain/>

Before downloading the module from CVS, let us set an environment variable for our base directory to avoid confusion (you should choose a location where you would like to develop your analysis module and interface with CVS). Since the PHENIX environment uses a tcsh shell, the command you should use is the following:

```
setenv BASEDIR /path/to/desired/directory
echo $BASEDIR
cd $BASEDIR
```

To download a module from CVS,

```
cvs checkout offline/AnalysisTrain/ModuleName
```

In this case,

```
ModuleName = ExampleElectronSvxAnalysis
```

.

To compile this module and test locally, the executable macro will be required. To retrieve this

```
cvs checkout offline/AnalysisTrain/pat/macro/Run_ExampleSvxElectron.C
cvs checkout offline/AnalysisTrain/pat/macro/RunMyMacro.C
```

Only one example data file for each dataset is stored on an accessible disk to test the code. In order to run on the entire dataset, the analysis taxi needs to be submitted. This will be discussed later.

Before running locally, the module needs to be compiled. Steps to compile and run the example module are outline below:

```
cd $BASEDIR/offline/AnalysisTrain/ExampleElectronSvxAnalysis
./autogen.sh --prefix=$MYINSTALL
make
make install

cd $BASEDIR/offline/AnalysisTrain/pat/macro
root -l 'RunMyMacro.C("Run_ExampleSvxElectron.C","output.root",20000,
"Run15pp200CAERTP108")'
```

Make sure \$MYINSTALL is predefined – you will also need to update your \$LD_LIBRARY_PATH environment variable to point to the directory where your newly compiled libraries are, which you can do with the following command:

```
setenv LD_LIBRARY_PATH $MYINSTALL/lib:${LD_LIBRARY_PATH}
```

"Run15pp200CAERTP108" is the code name defining to the dataset (200 GeV run 15 p+p ERT data in this case) – you can also try "Run15pp200CAMBP108" for 200 GeV run 15 p+p minbias data. 20000 is the number of events on which the code is tested. Use 0 to run on the entire file. Each file typically has around 2M events.

4 Committing the module

Before committing files to CVS, the permission needs to be unlocked using

```
klog.krb5
```

The password would be your RCF account password. Once unlocked, new module can be added using

```
cd $BASEDIR/offline/AnalysisTrain/
cvs add YourModule
cvs update YourModule
cd YourModule
cvs add (each file individually)
cvs commit -m "message" (each file individually)
```

Make sure that `autogen.sh` is executable before uploading to CVS.

```
chmod 755 autogen.sh
```

The executable macro accompanying the analysis module should be named `Run_YourExecutable.C` and is uploaded using

```
cd $BASEDIR/offline/AnalysisTrain/pat/macro
cvs add Run_YourExecutable.C
cvs commit -m "message" Run_YourExecutable.C
```

To commit files after editing (they only need to be added to CVS once),

```
cvs commit -m "message" filename
```

It is good practice to include the changes made in the message. We can now move on to testing our code is robust enough to process the full dataset without any errors such as memory leaks.

5 The Gatekeeper

The analysis taxi will allow you to process the entirety of a dataset using your analysis module, but first it will run various checks to ensure there are no memory leaks or initialization errors – this is known as the gatekeeper, and consists of your module being tested against `cppcheck`, `valgrind`, and `insure`. It is good practice to perform these checks yourself before submitting an analysis taxi job.

5.1 `cppcheck`

`Cppcheck` is a static analysis tool that is useful for finding issues with code written in C or C++, more information can be found here <http://cppcheck.sourceforge.net/>. In order to run `cppcheck`, you want to run the following commands:

```
cd $BASEDIR/offline/AnalysisTrain/YourModule
cppcheck --language=c++ *.h *.C
```

If your module passes the check with no explicit error or warning messages, then you are good to proceed to the next step of the gatekeeper. To see an explicit example of `cppcheck` output, I have included the output for the example module `ExampleElectronSvxAnalysis`:

```
Checking ConversionVeto.C ...
1/5 files checked 35% done
Checking ConversionVeto.h ...
2/5 files checked 53% done
Checking ExampleElectronSvxAnalysis.C ...
3/5 files checked 94% done
Checking ExampleElectronSvxAnalysis.h ...
4/5 files checked 99% done
Checking ExampleElectronSvxAnalysisLinkDef.h ...
Checking ExampleElectronSvxAnalysisLinkDef.h: __CINT__...
5/5 files checked 100% done
```

It can be seen that the standard check produced no errors or warning messages, just as desired, meaning we are okay to proceed with the next step of the gatekeeper. You may also be interested in obtaining more verbose output with suggestions to help improve your coding style. If this is desired, you can use the "--enable=all" flag, as follows:

```
cd $BASEDIR/offline/AnalysisTrain/YourModule
cppcheck --language=c++ --enable=all *.h *.C
```

You will see that this likely produces much more output with suggestions categorized under "style". Feel free to implement the suggestions if you would like to clean up your code – this will get you in the habit of using better coding practices, but this step is not necessary for passing the gatekeeper.

5.2 Valgrind

Valgrind is an analysis tool that relies on you compiling and executing your code to meticulously check for memory leaks. Running your code with Valgrind can take significantly longer than normal, so it is recommended that you test with a small sample of 200 events. You will ultimately need to execute the RunMyMacro.C script using Valgrind, so you will need to make sure you are in the proper directory before launching the Valgrind command – this can all be achieved with the following steps:

```
cd $BASEDIR/offline/AnalysisTrain/pat/macro
valgrind -v --num-callers=40 --leak-check=full --error-limit=no \
  --log-file=valgrind.log --suppressions=$ROOTSYS/root.supp \
  --leak-resolution=high root.exe
```

This command will launch the ROOT prompt, from which you will need to execute the macro RunMyMacro.C as follows (this is shown for testing our example module here):

```
.x RunMyMacro.C("Run_ExampleSvxElectron.C", "output.root", 200,
  "Run15pp200CAERTP108")
```

This will take some time to process, but once it is finished it will produce an "output.root" file as well as a "valgrind.log" file. You want to check the "valgrind.log" file to ensure that there were no memory leaks during the test. To do this, you can enter the following command to your terminal:

```
tail valgrind.log
```

The tail command spits out the last few lines of the log file to the terminal. Here is an example of the output from testing the ExampleElectronSvxAnalysis module – note that I am only including the last line of the log file as it is the only one that is relevant here:

```
==29236== ERROR SUMMARY: 0 errors from 0 contexts (suppressed: 1137863 from 447)
```

This is exactly what we are looking for – it indicates that Valgrind detected no memory leaks in your analysis module. It also indicates that you are all set to proceed to the final step of the gatekeeper!

5.3 Insure

Insure is a tool that is similar to Valgrind in that it requires compiling and executing your code on a small set of data to test for memory leaks and ensure it is running efficiently (see what I did there?). This time you want to execute the macro RunMyMacro.C using insure, the necessary commands follow:

```
cd $BASEDIR/offline/AnalysisTrain/pat/macro
root_insure.exe
```

This command will launch the ROOT prompt, from which you will need to execute the macro RunMyMacro.C as follows (this is shown for testing our example module here):

```
.x RunMyMacro.C("Run_ExampleSvxElectron.C", "output.root", 200,
"Run15pp200CAERTP108")
```

This will again take some time to process, but once it is finished it will produce an "output.root" file as well as an "insure.report" file. You want to check the "insure.report" file to ensure that there were no memory leaks – we can again use the tail command:

```
tail insure.report
```

Here is an example of the output from testing the ExampleElectronSvxAnalysis module:

```
READ_WILD: Reading wild pointer, 2 unique occurrences
    765 at PC: 0xf6afb330
    1 at PC: 0xf724c014
No leaks were found.
```

Again, the "no leaks were found" message at the end of the file is exactly what we are looking for to verify a successful test. Once this final check is complete, you have now verified for yourself that your analysis module will pass the analysis taxi gatekeeper – woohoo! Now you can submit your job to the analysis taxi to process large samples of data.

6 Submitting to the Analysis Taxi

The analysis taxi leverages a high performance computing cluster to process many files in parallel, allowing for analysis of entire collected datasets from given running periods. Once the analysis module is tested, committed to CVS, and passing gatekeeper checks, analysis taxi jobs can be submitted to process the entire dataset. To do this the following website is used.

<https://phenix-intra.sdcc.bnl.gov/WWW/p/draft/anatrain/register/taxiRegForm.html>

The entries in the form are explained below:

- Name : your name
- E-mail : your email address
- Macro name : Run_YourExecutable.C
- Analysis code directories : YourModule

- PWG disk : the working group where you have your directory (e.g. spin in case of /phenix/spin/phnxsp01/username)
- User name : username
- Select the dataset you would like to run on (in case of the example, under Run 15 pp 200 GeV Central Arm, select Run-15 200 GeV p+p pro108 (ERT) or (MinBias))
- DST types : Select all applicable (in case of the example CNT, DST_EVE, and DST_SVX)
- Aggregation : choose Yes if you would like the output to be written out by run number
- Event mixing : depends on your analysis (in this example, no)
- Run number list : provide if you can (can also remove bad runs in output directory with shell scripting since files are output and named by run number – at least if aggregation is on)
- Estimated disk space : can obtain estimate by multiplying ratio of total events in dataset (on taxi registration form) vs number of tested events with RunMyMacro.C by the output file size from RunMyMacro.C
- Additional requests : if you have any

Submit the form when done.

The output from taxi (TTrees/histograms) can be found in

`/phenix/(PWG disk name)/username/taxi`

Note: Different working groups may have slightly different directory structure... (e.g. for Spin – /phenix/spin/phnxsp01/username/taxi).

7 Characteristics plots

An example macro to analyze the analysis taxi output trees, apply all selection requirements listed in this document, and make histograms is included in the analysis module (it is called "MyAnalysis.C"). Please note that this is NOT a standard macro to include in analysis modules designated for the taxi – I only include it here for completeness of the electron identification tutorial. Figure 1 shows the distribution of E/p and $n0$ of electron candidates from the SvxCentralTrackList collection, with all selection requirements listed in this document applied, as seen in Run 15 p+p collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 200$ GeV on a subset of 1 million events.

Figure 1: Distribution of E/p (left panel) and n_0 (right panel) for electron candidates from SvxCentralTracks with all selection requirements listed in this document applied.

Figure 2 shows the distribution of E/p and n_0 of electron candidates from the SvxCentralTrack-List collection, with all selection requirements listed in this document applied except those that rely explicitly on SvxCentralTrack information, as seen in Run 15 p+p collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 200$ GeV on a subset of 1 million events. One notices a significant increase in statistics with respect to Figure 1, but at the price of introducing a larger fraction of photonic electrons into the data sample.

Figure 2: Distribution of E/p (left panel) and n_0 (right panel) for electron candidates from SvxCentralTracks with all selection requirements listed in this document applied except for those that rely explicitly on SvxCentralTrack information.

Finally, Figure 3 shows the distribution of E/p and n_0 of electron candidates from the PH-CentralTrack collection, with all selection requirements listed in this document applied except those that rely explicitly on SvxCentralTrack information, as seen in Run 15 p+p collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 200$ GeV on a subset of 1 million events. One notices another significant increase in statistics with respect to Figure 2, again at the price of introducing a larger fraction of photonic electrons into the data sample, and the loss of SvxCentralTrack information that is crucial to decrease this photonic electron fraction. Note that Figures 2 and 3 have the same selection requirements applied – the key difference is that Figure 2 comes from the SvxCentralTrack-List collection, while Figure 3 comes from the PHCentralTrack collection. That means the distributions in Figure 2 come from candidates that additionally meet the minimum criteria for SvxCentralTrack reconstruction, which amongst other things, includes a hit in at least 2 layers of the VTX and a match to a track in the PHCentralTrack collection, hence the significant difference in statistics.

Figure 3: Distribution of E/p (left panel) and n_0 (right panel) for electron candidates from PHCentralTracks with all selection requirements listed in this document applied except those that rely explicitly on SvxCentralTrack information.

In summary, one should adjust the selection requirements depending on what type of analysis they are doing – i.e. if your signal is nonphotonic electrons vs. photonic electrons. It would be a good exercise to make simulations in PISA for electron candidates (both nonphotonic and photonic), and charged hadrons, in order to test the probability of each type passing the selection requirements, allowing one to determine the electron purity of the data sample.

8 Additional Information

While this tutorial is focused on electron identification at PHENIX, typical analyses require a bit of extra information, such as trigger information for cross section measurements, or spin database information for spin asymmetry measurements. Functionality for accessing trigger and spin database information in run 15 p+p 200 GeV data is included in the analysis module (specifically the ExampleElectronSvxAnalysis class) for you to investigate!